

Fact Sheet

Project information

HIVACS

Grant agreement ID: 831838

Status

Ongoing project

Start date

1 April 2019

End date

28 February 2021

Funded under:

H2020-EU.3.4.5.1.

Overall budget:

€ 853 798,96

EU contribution

€ 749 833,50

Coordinated by:

IRT ANTOINE DE SAINT EXUPERY

 France

Objective

Current research and development is focusing on propulsive energy components for hybrid aircraft. This will open the path to an all-electrical aircraft. Power levels are predicted to be between 2 and 4MVA for hybrid systems and up to 40MVA for all electrical systems. This will require the transmission of electrical power across the airframe at previously unseen scales. This will not be possible without the development of power dense and safe cabling systems that operate at higher levels of voltage and current. To this end, the objective of HIVACS is to bring together a coherent suite of experimentally validated simulation models to permit the design exploration and optimisation of future aerospace cable systems to allow the aeronautical industry to meet the high-power design requirements of future aircraft programs. The project will also provide recommendations for future standardisation to the relevant standard committees and identify key axis for further development. After performing a state-of-the art review, a requirements and Failure Mode Effect and Analysis (FMEA) will be performed on the design and manufacturing processes on a selection of designs. A range of existing models will be used to assess the performance of these designs with these being adapted to the aerospace environment. The models will be validated by comparison to experimental test bench activities undertaken on existing cables. Once the models are qualified and accepted by NEXANS as being appropriate for adoption in an industrial setting, they will be used in a design optimisation process to determine optimal geometry and sizing of the candidate cables and predict their expected performance. With an optimum cable design, two cable types will be produced using different manufacturing techniques. Both will be tested and qualified. The project will draw upon existing test bench facilities and also develop a specific thermal test bench for thermal cycling ageing.

Field of Science

/engineering and technology/mechanical engineering/vehicle engineering/aerospace engineering/aircraft

/natural sciences/mathematics/pure mathematics/geometry

Programme(s)

[H2020-EU.3.4.5.1. - IADP Large Passenger Aircraft](#)

Topic(s)

[JTI-CS2-2018-CfP08-LPA-01-55 - Development of AC cabling technologies for >1kV aerospace applications](#)

Call for proposal

H2020-CS2-CFP08-2018-01

[See other projects for this call](#)

Funding Scheme

CS2-IA - Innovation action

Coordinator

IRT ANTOINE DE SAINT EXUPERY

Address

B 612 - Cs 34436, 3 Rue

Tarfaya

31400 Toulouse

France

[Contact the organisation](#)

Activity type

Research Organisations

EU Contribution

€ 261 451,25

Participants ⁽³⁾

NEXANS FRANCE

 France

EU Contribution

€ 184 069,75

Address

4 Allee De L'Arche
92400 Courbevoie

Activity type

**Private for-profit entities
(excluding Higher or
Secondary Education
Establishments)**

[Website](#)

[Contact the organisation](#)

UNIVERSITE PAUL SABATIER TOULOUSE III

 France

EU Contribution

€ 139 312,50

Address

Route De Narbonne 118
31062 Toulouse Cedex 9

Activity type

**Higher or Secondary
Education Establishments**

[Website](#)

[Contact the organisation](#)

THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER

 United Kingdom

EU Contribution

€ 165 000

Address

Oxford Road
M13 9pl Manchester

Activity type

**Higher or Secondary
Education Establishments**

[Website](#)

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